

Synthesis of Antifungal Pyrazolones and Related Compounds

S. P. SUMAN AND S. C. BAHTEL

Chemistry Department, University of Gorakhpur, Gorakhpur (U. P.)

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Three N_1 -aryloxyacetyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolones, twenty 4-arylidene- N_1 -aryloxyacetyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolones, twenty bis(N_1 -aryloxyacetyl-3-Me-5-pyrazolone-5-yl) arylmethanes and eighteen 4-bromo-(4- α -bromoaryl)- N_1 -aryloxyacetyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolones have been synthesised with a view to study their antifungal activity. Some of the compounds have been screened for their antifungal activity against '*A. niger*' and '*A. flavus*' and found to be antifungal.

THERAPEUTICAL importance of pyrazolone and its derivatives has been studied by several investigators as bactericides and fungicides^{1,2}. Some halogenated and non-halogenated pyrazolones have been screened as fungicides^{3,4}. Working on the generalization that N-heterocycles incorporated with CO group show significant pesticidal activity^{5,6}, we have prepared the title compounds which possess an additional CO group directly linked with the pyrazolone ring leading thereby to a possible enhanced activity.

N_1 -Aryloxyacetyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolones (I) required in this work, have been obtained by the reaction of aryloxyacetyl-hydrazines with ethyl acetoacetate⁷. Reaction of (I) with arylaldehyde in glacial acetic acid gave their monoarylidene derivatives (II) along with bis-pyrazolone compounds (III), which were isolated by diluting the solution after separation of (II). The

monoarylidene compounds (II) obtained were brominated with bromine in acetic acid to give 4-bromo-(4- α -bromoaryl)- N_1 -aryloxyacetyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolones (IV).

The analytical data of compounds, thus obtained are summarised in Tables 1-4.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected.

Aryloxyacetylhydrazines :

These were prepared by the method of L. Conti⁸.

N_1 -Aryloxyacetyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolones⁷ (I) :

To an ethanolic suspension (20 ml) of aryloxyacetylhydrazine (0.01M), ethylacetoacetate (0.01M) was added and the mixture refluxed for three hours. On evaporation a solid was obtained which was washed and crystallised.

4-Arylidene- N_1 -aryloxyacetyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolones (II) :

An arylaldehyde (0.01M) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (5ml). This was added to a glacial acetic acid

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF (I)

S. No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Found	N%	Calcd.
1.	2,6-Me ₂ -Ph-	145	90	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	12.00		12.00
2.	3-Me-4-iC ₃ H ₇ -Ph-	90	87	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	10.62		10.76
3.	4-tert-C ₄ H ₉ -Ph-	105	80	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	10.68		10.76

All the compounds gave satisfactory analysis for C and H.

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S. No.	R	TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA OF (II)		Molecular formula	N%	
		M.P. °C	Yield % R = 2,6-Me ₂ -Ph-		Found	Calcd.
1.	Ph-	185	55	C ₂₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂	8.70	8.75
2.	2-Cl-Ph-	170	60	C ₂₀ H ₉ ClN ₂ O ₂	—	7.89
3.	3-Cl-Ph-	164	55	C ₂₀ H ₉ ClN ₂ O ₂	7.84	7.89
4.	4-Cl-Ph-	181	62	C ₂₀ H ₉ ClN ₂ O ₂	7.80	7.89
5.	2-OH-Ph-	160	50	C ₂₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃	8.21	8.33
6.	3-OH-Ph-	150	42	C ₂₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃	—	8.33
7.	4-OH-Ph-	175	53	C ₂₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃	8.25	8.33
8.	4-Me ₂ N-Ph-	139	44	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	11.51	11.57
9.	4-CH ₃ O-Ph-	145	48	C ₂₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂	7.91	8.00
10.	PhCH=CH-	133	40	C ₂₂ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂	8.03	8.11
R = 3-Me-4-iC ₂ H ₇ -Ph-						
11.	Ph-	170	50	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂	—	8.04
12.	2-Cl-Ph-	162	50	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ ClN ₂ O ₂	—	7.32
13.	3-Cl-Ph-	154	47	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ ClN ₂ O ₂	—	7.32
14.	4-Cl-Ph-	159	52	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ ClN ₂ O ₂	7.30	7.32
15.	2-OH-Ph-	165	50	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₃	7.60	7.69
16.	3-OH-Ph-	142	42	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₃	—	7.69
17.	4-OH-Ph-	150	54	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₃	—	7.69
18.	4-Me ₂ N-Ph-	135	48	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	10.70	10.74
19.	4-MeO-Ph-	150	42	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	7.33	7.40
20.	Ph-CH=CH	120	35	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂	7.42	7.50

— not analysed.

S. No.	R'	TABLE 3—ANALYTICAL DATA OF (III)		Molecular formula	N%	
		M.P. °C	Yield % R = 2,6-Me ₂ Ph-		Found	Calcd.
1.	Ph-	160	40	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄	10.02	10.14
2.	2-Cl-Ph-	150	33	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ O ₄	9.50	9.54
3.	4-Cl-Ph-	170	35	CC ₂₂ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ O ₄	—	9.54
4.	4-Cl-Ph-	170	35	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ O ₄	—	9.54
5.	2-OH-Ph-	140	35	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₅	9.81	9.85
6.	3-OH-Ph-	132	30	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₅	—	9.85
7.	4-OH-Ph-	158	38	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₅	9.79	9.85
8.	4-Me ₂ N-Ph-	130	40	C ₂₅ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₄	—	11.76
9.	4-MeO-Ph-	120	42	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₅	9.53	9.62
10.	Ph-CH=CH-	101	40	C ₂₅ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₄	9.67	9.70

Contd.

Table 3 Contd.

S. No.	R'	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular Formula	Found	N%	
						Found	Calcd.
R=3-Me-4-iC ₇ H ₇ -Ph-							
11.	Ph-	155	42	C ₂₅ H ₄₀ N ₄ O ₄	9.15		9.21
12.	2-Cl-Ph-	148	36	C ₂₅ H ₃₉ ClN ₄ O ₄	—		8.71
13.	3-Cl-Ph-	140	30	C ₂₅ H ₃₉ ClN ₄ O ₄	8.61		8.71
14.	4-Cl-Ph-	152	35	C ₂₅ H ₃₉ ClN ₄ O ₄	—		8.71
15.	2-OH-Ph-	135	42	C ₂₅ H ₄₀ N ₄ O ₅	8.91		8.97
16.	3-OH-Ph-	120	35	C ₂₅ H ₄₀ N ₄ O ₅	—		8.97
17.	4-OH-Ph-	143	40	C ₂₅ H ₄₀ N ₄ O ₅	—		8.97
18.	4-Me ₂ N-Ph-	115	33	C ₂₇ H ₄₅ N ₅ O ₄	10.90		10.92
19.	4-MeO-Ph-	114	43	C ₂₆ H ₄₃ N ₄ O ₅	8.71		8.77
20.	Ph-CH=CH-	105	42	C ₂₇ H ₄₁ N ₄ O ₄	8.80		8.84

— not analysed.

TABLE 4—ANALYTICAL DATA OF (IV)

S. No.	R'	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Found	N%	
						Found	Calcd.
T=2,6-Me ₂ Ph-							
1.	Ph-	135	90	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂	5.77		5.83
2.	2-Cl-Ph-	120	92	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ Br ₂ ClN ₂ O ₂	5.41		5.44
3.	3-Cl-Ph-	110	90	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ Br ₂ ClN ₂ O ₂	—		5.44
4.	4-Cl-Ph-	126	95	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ Br ₂ ClN ₂ O ₂	—		5.44
5.	2-OH-Ph-	110	82	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₃	5.59		5.64
6.	3-OH-Ph-	90	70	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₃	5.57		5.64
7.	4-OH-Ph-	113	90	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₃	—		5.64
8.	4-Me ₂ N-Ph-	85	74	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂	8.00		8.03
9.	4-MeO-Ph-	76	87	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂	5.43		5.49
R=3-Me-4-iC ₇ H ₇ -Ph-							
10.	Ph-	115	92	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂	5.47		5.51
11.	2-Cl-Ph-	104	96	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ Br ₂ ClN ₂ O ₂	5.11		5.16
12.	3-Cl-Ph-	92	80	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ Br ₂ ClN ₂ O ₂	—		5.16
13.	4-Cl-Ph-	109	89	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ Br ₂ ClN ₂ O ₂	—		5.16
14.	2-OH-Ph-	84	78	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₃	5.24		5.34
15.	3-OH-Ph-	78	70	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₃	5.28		5.34
16.	4-OH-Ph-	93	84	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₃	—		5.34
17.	4-Me ₂ N-Ph-	70	80	C ₂₄ H ₂₉ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂	7.70		7.76
18.	4-MeO-Ph-	74	86	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂	5.12		5.20

All the compounds gave satisfactory analysis for bromine.

— not analysed.

(15 ml) solution of N_1 -aryloxyacetyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone (0.01M) and resulting solution kept in a refrigerator until a product separated out (1 hr to 20 days). It was filtered, washed with cold glacial acetic acid, water and crystallised with methanol.

Arylidene bis-pyrazolones(III) [*Bis-(N₁-aryloxyacetyl-3-Me-5-pyrazolone-5-yl)-arylmethane*]⁹ :

After separating the (II), the filtrate was diluted with water and the solution kept in the refrigerator until a product separated out (at 12 to 30 hours). It was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallized with methanol.

4-Bromo-(4- α -bromoaryl)-N₁-aryloxyacetyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolones(IV) :

To the suspension of 4-arylidene- N_1 -aryloxyacetyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone (0.005M) in acetic acid (20 ml), bromine in acetic acid was added dropwise with constant stirring till the color of bromine persisted. The mixture was kept overnight, when a solid separated out. It was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised with methanol.

Fungicidal activity :

All the compounds of Table 1, ten compounds (1, 2, 5, 8, 9, 10, 13, 17, 18 and 20) of Table 2, nine compounds of Table 3 (1, 3, 7, 8, 10, 14, 17, 18 and 20) and nine compounds of Table 4 (1, 3, 5, 8, 9, 11, 14, 17 and 28) were screened for their antifungal activity against '*A. niger*' and '*A. flavus*' by agar plate technique^{10,11} at three different concentrations namely, 1:1,000, 1:10,000 and 1:100,000. The compounds

screened were found to show antifungal activity. All the compounds derived from pyrazolones show higher fungicidal activity than the parent compounds. In general, antifungal activity has been found to increase in the order I, II, III, IV. The different groups of the aldehyde moiety do not show any significant effect towards the antifungal activity.

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